

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF FARMERS PRACTICING APPLE-BASED AGROFORESTRY IN THE WET TEMPERATE REGION OF MANDI DISTRICT, HIMACHAL PRADESH

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Abstract

The present study was conducted in the Mandi District of Himachal Pradesh, to investigate the apple-based agroforestry system to assess the demographic characteristics and socio-economic status of farmers. A multistage random sampling technique was used to select the study site. The methodology comprised of site selection, sampling procedure, identification of the cropping pattern with the apple tree, data collection, analytical framework and valuation in different altitudinal zones A1 (1500-1800m), A2 (1801-2100m), A3 (2101-2400m) and A4 (2401-2700m). The study revealed that farmers in the Mandi district were growing various agricultural crops under apple trees and additionally, farmers have retained various grass species during Kharif and Rabi seasons. The marginal, small, and semi-medium farmers have been practicing the above mentioned explained practices of growing agriculture crops and grasses with apple tree in the area. The variation in the average family size among different farmers category lies between 5.28 to 5.94 and the highest average family size was recorded at altitudinal zone-I. The maximum average sex ratio was observed at altitudinal zone III. The higher number of nuclear families were recorded at altitudinal zone-I, while the maximum joint families were found at altitudinal zone-IV. The literacy per cent in district ranged between 79.42 to 82.77 % with maximum at altitudinal zone-I. The average cow per family was maximum (1.41) at altitudinal zone-IV and semi-medium farmers reared maximum cows compared to all categories. Most of the farmers were engaged to horticulture sector, the maximum (81.26%) male and female were at altitudinal zone-IV. The average land holding area was found to be maximum (2.42 ha) in semi-medium. Therefore, the apple-based agroforestry system in the wet temperate region of Himachal Pradesh is recommended for its social, economic, and environmental benefits to support the rural population's livelihood and food security in the era of climate change.

Keywords: Apple-based agroforestry system, Cropping pattern, Climate change, Livelihood improvement, Landholding

Introduction

Agroforestry is a multifunctional method that involves the deliberate integration of trees and shrubs with crops or livestock on the same piece of land for the betterment of human life. For over 50 years, this sustainable agricultural practice has been recognized (Aryal et al., 2023). It is a promising land use strategy in both developed and developing regions, offering economic, ecological, and cultural benefits and providing a wide range of goods, including crops, fruits, forages, cattle, biomass, and medicine (Sollen-Norrlin et al., 2020, Telwala, 2023; Vinals et al., 2023). Orchard farming has been practiced for over four decades, positively impacting the social and economic lives of the Himachal Pradesh people (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015). To ensure food security, it is essential to expand agricultural areas and boost crop productivity, using technology to help farmers withstand disruptions.

In India, the average per capita forest availability is merely 0.08 hectares, in contrast to the worldwide average of 0.64 hectares. Himachal Pradesh encompasses a total area of 55673 square kilometers, featuring a forest cover of 15,100 square kilometers. This forest cover represents 27.12% of the state's overall geographical area, as reported in the State of Forest Report (2017). While it is essential to meet the fundamental needs of the population, safeguarding our delicate and sensitive environment is also paramount (Singh, 2019). In this regard, the concept of agroforestry, where agricultural crops and forest tree species are integrated for the benefit of both people and the ecosystem seems to provide a promising solution. Apple-based agroforestry systems significantly enhance the livelihoods of farmers in various regions of HP and apples yield the highest financial returns while promoting ecological sustainability and improving the socioeconomic status of smallholder farmers (Singh, 2006). The state has witnessed a major shift in area from food grain towards horticulture crops over the last five years (Horticulture Development, HP, 2018). Systematic apple farming yields significantly greater profits, with a net income of 1.63 units for every unit invested in the region though this remains lower compared to other major apple-producing countries globally.

Over time, climate change and shifts in the rural economy have pushed farmers in Himachal Pradesh to shift away from traditional farming toward non-farm activities, resulting in a decline in agricultural productivity. Therefore, the apple-based agroforestry system is essential for addressing these challenges by promoting awareness of its

benefits in the region's hilly areas. The socioeconomic status of farmers greatly affects their agricultural practices and decision-making (Tiwari et al., 2018). Farmers with higher socioeconomic status typically have better access to resources such as quality seeds and modern technology, which leads to improved productivity. Addressing economic and social disparities is vital for encouraging beneficial farming methods, such as apple-based agroforestry. This approach is especially valuable in challenging hilly areas, where traditional farming can be difficult. By focusing on these disparities, we can support farmers in adopting more sustainable practices that enhance their livelihoods and benefit the environment. In the present study, the main focus is on the socioeconomic status of the Mandi district and understanding its impact on the livelihoods of farmers in the district.

Methodology

Location of the study area

The study was conducted in Mandi district, located between 31° 42' 25" N latitude and 76° 55' 54" E longitude. The elevation of the district ranges from 450 to 4800 meters. The major seasons in the district are: the winter season, which start from November to February; the summer season from March to June; the monsoon period last from July to the end of September with total annual rainfall of about 1516.1 mm in 2021 and 1617.3 mm in 2022. The average temperature during the summer season ranges between 16.0 °C to 35.0 °C and varies from 1.1 °C to 21.6 °C in the winter. The area falls under wet temperate agro-climatic zone. The survey was conducted in different village viz., Dobrot, Mahunag, Churag, Bulas, Aukal, Pandoh, Baila, Ruhada, Raindhar, Riyara, Dhalyar, and Janoot. The farmers were categorized in three sections as marginal (<1 ha), small (1-2 ha), semi-medium farmers (2-4 ha), on the basis of land holding size (Table 1).

Sampling procedure and Survey schedule

Using a pre-structured questionnaire, personal interviews and field-based observations were conducted during the survey. The selected farmers, preferably the heads of the household, were interviewed regarding the demographic features of their families, land holdings, and the various cropping practices implemented within apple-based agroforestry systems in the region, focusing on their economic perceptions of the system. Through this pre-structured questionnaire, a total of 180 farmers were surveyed during the year 2022-2023.

The primary data on demographic features such as family size, education, occupation, economic parameters, livestock, and cropping patterns were collected from the selected households in the study area.

Secondary data were also gathered from the records of the Department of Horticulture in Shimla, Himachal Pradesh, as well as from respective revenue offices and directorates of land records. To meet the requirements of the study objectives, simple tabular analysis was employed to examine the socio-economic status. For comparison, interpretation, and contrasting of the results, simple statistical tools such as averages and percentages were used. The socio-economic status was evaluated by calculating the sex ratio and literacy rate using the following formulae:

$$\text{Sex Ratio} = \frac{\text{No. of females in a family}}{\text{No. of males}} \times 1000$$

$$\text{Net return} = \text{Gross return} - \text{Total costs}$$

$$\text{Benefit / Cost ratio} = \frac{\text{Total Gross returns (Rs/ha)}}{\text{Total cost of cultivation (Rs/ha)}}$$

$$\text{Literacy Rate} = \frac{\text{Total no. of literate person}}{\text{Total population}} \times 100$$

Bio-economics of the Apple-based agroforestry systems

Cost of cultivation: Cost of cultivation was calculated on per hectare basis as per the market rates of inputs during the respective year.

Gross return: The market prices of the crops were used to convert the yield of all the crop plants into gross return in rupees per hectare.

Net return: It was calculated by deducting total cost from gross returns (Sharma et al. 2023).

Benefit cost ratio: The benefit cost ratio of the apple-based agroforestry system was calculated by dividing total discounted benefits with total discounted costs of the system (Sharma et al. 2023).

Table: 1. Different farmer's category, their operational land holding and number

Sr.no	Farmers categories*	Size of operational land holding	No. of farmers surveyed
1.	Marginal	<1 ha	45
2.	Small	1-2 ha	45
3.	Semi-medium	2-4 ha	45

Result and Discussion

Identified agroforestry systems based on apple, adopted by various categories of farmers in Mandi District (HP)

Altitudinal zone-I

Table 2 shows that the farmers in the study area adopted both types of apple-based agroforestry systems to enhance their livelihoods. Among the farmer categories at this altitudinal zone (A₁), the semi-medium farmers adopted (93.33 %) more diverse crops with apple trees than the other two farmer categories (Fig.1). Whereas in the same altitudinal zone, the small farmers had retained (100%) grasses on their agriculture and horticulture bunds to meet the required fodder for the livestock.

Altitudinal zone-II

In this zone, the semi-medium farmer adopted (93.33%) a wider variety of crops, including apple trees, compared to the other two farmer categories. In the same altitudinal zone, the semi-medium farmers retained (93.33%) grasses on their agricultural and horticultural land to meet the necessary fodder requirements for the livestock.

Altitudinal zone-III

The data presented in Table 2 indicates that the semi-medium farmer adopted a wider variety of agricultural crops intercropped with apple trees (93.33%), compared to the other two farmer categories. In the same altitudinal zone, small and semi-medium farmers maintained grasses on their agricultural and horticultural land (93.33%) to meet the necessary fodder requirements for livestock (Fig. 1).

Altitudinal zone-IV

The semi-medium farmer category adopted (86.67%) diverse crops with apple tree as compared to both farmer categories as mentioned in Table 2. While, the same farmers category has retained (93.33%) grasses on their farm field.

Socio-economic status of different farmers category in altitudinal zones of Mandi district (H.P)

The socioeconomic status constitutes a critical determinant of the health conditions of individuals or families. Various variables collectively determine farmers economic and social position, encompassing factors such as income, education, occupation, family, physical assets, social standing, caste, political influence, and

participation in social activities. Socioeconomic status serves as a comprehensive measure, quantifying the economic and social status of an individual or family (Gaur, 2013).

Family structure

Among different altitudinal zones maximum (5.94) average family structure was recorded at A₁ and minimum (5.28) was recorded at A₄. While among different farmers category, the maximum (6.22) average family structure was recorded for semi-medium category and minimum (5.03) was recorded for the marginal farmers category (Table 3 & Fig. 3).

Literacy (%)

A perusal of the data presented in Table 3 represents that the maximum (87.22%) literacy percentage was found at A₁ and the minimum (79.42%) was found at A₂ (fig. 2).

Among different farmer categories, the maximum (81.63%) literacy rate was found among marginal farmer and minimum (81.27%) was recorded among semi-medium farmers category.

Livestock status

Among different altitudinal zones, maximum (1.41) average livestock was reared by farmers at A₄, and minimum (1.14) was reared at A₁. While among different farmers category, the maximum (1.41) average livestock was recorded for the semi-medium category and minimum (1.23) was recorded for small farmer's category (Table 3 & Fig. 3).

Status of occupation (Agrarian people)

Among different farmers category, the maximum (3.61) average farmers of small category were engaged in agriculture sector, while minimum (3.27) average farmers of the marginal category were also engaged in agriculture sector (Table 3 & Fig. 3). At A₄ altitudinal zone maximum (3.75) average farmers were engaged in agriculture sector whereas, At A₁, minimum (2.86) were recorded in engaged in agriculture sector.

Land holding (ha)

Among different altitudinal zones, the maximum (1.51) average land holding was recorded at A₂, and minimum (1.45) was recorded at A₁. While among different farmers category, the maximum (2.40) average land holding was recorded for the semi-medium farmer and the minimum (0.71) was recorded for marginal farmer (Table 3 & Fig. 3).

Table: 4. Comparative bio-economic performance of two Apple-based agroforestry systems in Mandi, Himachal Pradesh.

Apple based system	Total expenses (₹ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Gross return (₹ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Net return (₹ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Benefit: cost ratio
Horti-agriculture	622720	1545582	922862	2.50

Horti-pasture	516547	1138542	621995	1.94
t stat value	2.32*	2.66*	2.14*	2.14*

t-table value: 2.07 *significant

As data presented in Table 4, the t-stat value of Total expense (2.32), Gross return (2.66), Net return (2.14) and for BCR (2.14) is greater than the t-table value (2.07), therefore, these two apple-based agroforestry systems are statistically significant with each other.

Discussion

Identified agroforestry systems based on apple, adopted by various categories of farmers in Mandi District (HP)

The current study examined the importance of the apple-based agroforestry system used by various farmer categories across different altitudinal zones in the Mandi district. In India, about 58% of the population depends on agriculture as a primary source of income, with the combined sectors of agriculture, forestry, and fishery contributing a value of Rs 19.48 lakh crore (US\$ 276.37 billion) in the fiscal year 2020. The aim of the agroforestry is to reduce pressure from sole cropping by encouraging farmers to adopt suitable agroforestry systems. The practice was also highlighted in NITI Aayog (2024), which integrates the cultivation of trees alongside crops, promoting biodiversity and improving soil health. By diversifying their farming systems, farmers can enhance resilience against climate change, ecosystem services, and also contribute to sustainable land management. The analysis focused on the environmental benefits of a system through engagement with local farmers. The primary objectives were to assess their adaptation to the system and evaluate its effectiveness in real-world conditions, which provided valuable insights for future improvements. The current study revealed that 93.33% of farmers engaged in intercropping with various agricultural crops and maintained diverse grasses alongside apple trees to meet their needs. Their crop choices are influenced by market prices and family labor availability, impacting both economic viability and agricultural resilience. The combination of subsistence and commercial farming practices enhances farmers livelihoods, fostering beneficial interactions among the plants during the growing season. Intercropping with agricultural crops is essential for enhancing crop productivity and soil fertility through atmospheric nitrogen fixation (Tripathi and Tauseef, 2018). Abera et al. (2025) found that 36% of farmers adopted home gardens, 29.71% incorporated scattered trees, 16% practiced boundary tree planting, and 2.29% utilized hedgerows. Those employing agroforestry practices enjoyed higher profitability rates of 16.54% compared to 9% for non-adopters, demonstrating the significant economic benefits and support for smallholder farmers' livelihoods.

Socio-economic status: In current study the farmers were categorized based on their landholdings into three classes: marginal (<1 ha), small (1-2 ha), and semi-medium (2-4 ha). It highlights that family size and structure significantly influence the adoption of apple-based agroforestry systems. In Mandi district, the average family size among different farmer categories ranges from 5.03 to 6.22. Semi-medium farmers tend to adopt apple agroforestry more due to their larger family size, which allows them to hire more labor. Legesse et al. (2025) highlight land size as a key factor, indicating that larger land-owners are more likely to invest in agricultural systems. This aligns with previous studies on family sizes in Himachal Pradesh, which reveal regional variations. Joshi (2011) found averages of 6.5 to 7.0 in Sirmour, while Nisha (2013) reported 5.53 among medium farmers in the mid-hills. Yadav et al. (2016) observed averages of 4.3 to 5.0 in Kumaon Himalaya, and Masoodi (2010) noted 5.00 in Solan. Additionally, Janju (2021) reported family sizes from 4.88 to 5.39 in Mandi, and Sharma (2022) provided averages of 5.58 to 5.96 in the mid and high hill zones. These findings underscore the influence of family size on agricultural practices across different regions.

Literacy (%)

The literacy percentage is an important indicator of educational status, particularly for marginal farmers, and it is linked to positive outcomes in agriculture. The literacy rates in the study area align with the

NAAS Rating – 04.17

regional statistics of 79.40 to 81.53% from 2020 and the 2011 Census. Higher educational levels among farmers facilitated the adoption of agroforestry systems and improved access to online resources, leading to better decision-making and enhanced agricultural productivity. The study also highlights educational status through Table 3.

Livestock

Livestock is crucial for the livelihoods of rural communities and the economies of developing nations. In agroforestry systems that rely on livestock, crops and animals coexist beneficially: crops provide fodder for various animals, including cows, bulls, goats, and sheep, which inhabit different elevations. Cattle are the most common species in this category. This study reveals that semi-medium farmers have the highest livestock averages at 1.41. According to Kumari et al. (2024), medium farmers average 2.39 livestock, while small and marginal farmers report 2.23 and 1.97, respectively, in Baijnath tehsil, Himachal Pradesh. Janju (2021) found similar livestock ranges (1.51 to 1.73) in the Seraj Valley, supported by Thakur (2020) in Chuhar Valley.

Our findings align with Tiwari et al. (2018), who note the importance of bovines in the north-western Himalayas. Livestock farming supports apple-based agroforestry, improving farmers' socioeconomic status and soil fertility through manure application (Nair and Toth, 2016). All households in apple orchards used cattle dung as fertilizer, promoting nutrient cycling, as reported by Harris (2002) and others.

Status of occupation (Agrarian people)

Understanding the occupation status of individuals is essential key to empowering farming communities to improve practices and adopt advanced technologies. Data from Table 3 showed that in the wet temperate region, semi-medium category farmers were engaged in agriculture at rates between 31.71% and 42.64%. The highest agricultural involvement was in altitudinal zone III, while zone I had the least. This finding aligns with DSO (2020), where about 40.00% to 45.00% of the local workforce involved in agriculture was noted, supported by studies from Janju (2020), Singh (2019), and Sharma (2022). Additionally, higher altitudes are beneficial for apple cultivation (Khan et al., 2023), highlighting opportunities for enhanced productivity.

Land holding

Land is a crucial resource in agrarian economies, greatly affecting household income, consumption, and profits. Our analysis shows a positive correlation between landholding size and different farmer categories, with average sizes ranging from 0.67 hectares to 2.42 hectares for marginal, small, and semi-medium farmers. This aligns with findings from DSO 2020, which reports average landholdings in Himachal Pradesh between 0.40 hectares and 2.72 hectares. Upadhyaya (1997) found similar land use statistics in Balh Valley, while Janju (2021) reported a range of 0.71 hectares to 2.54 hectares in Mandi district, supporting our conclusions. Tiwari et al. (2018) also documented this positive correlation in Sirmour district. Overall, these findings highlight the significant role of land size in shaping farmer livelihoods.

Economics of measures of farm profitability

The primary aim of agroforestry systems is to optimize economic returns per unit area by integrating trees and crops. In Mandi district, farmers are successfully combining various crops and grasses with apple trees, significantly boosting their income. The horti-agriculture system demonstrates the highest expenses of ₹ 622720 ha-1 yr-1, alongside impressive gross returns of ₹ 1545582 ha-1 yr-1 and net returns of ₹ 922862 ha-1 yr-1, achieving a favorable b:c ratio of 2.50 and outperforming the horti-pasture system. These higher costs are linked to increased inputs like seeds, irrigation, and fertilizers, but the returns justify these investments.

Supporting studies indicated that mixed systems generally incur higher expenses but yield better returns than pasture-based systems. The horti-agriculture system, particularly with high-value crops such as peas and

broccoli, showed greater net returns, while the horti-pasture system struggled with lower market values for grasses, reflecting findings observed by researchers in Himachal Pradesh, including Sood (1999), Toppo (2012), and Sharma (2022).

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that the socio-economic dynamics of farmers in Mandi district, such as family size, literacy (%), livestock status, occupation status and land holding significantly influence the adoption and sustainability of apple-based agroforestry system in wet temperate zone of H.P. By addressing gender imbalances and promoting higher educational attainment, positive correlation between landholding size and different farmer categories, agroforestry practices can be enhanced, contributing to food security and sustainable livelihoods. Effective livestock management is also crucial for increasing agricultural productivity and supporting rural livelihoods. It is essential to tackle challenges related to land holding size and off-farm employment to achieve sustainable development. The study highlights the importance of agroforestry systems. It emphasizes the need for comprehensive strategies to optimize their benefits, especially through approaches like apple-based agroforestry system, which can farmer livelihoods. Future research should aim to overcome challenges related to adoption and ensure long-term sustainability.

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Table 1: Identified Apple-based agroforestry systems practiced by different farmer categories, Mandi District (HP).

Elevations	Horti-agriculture			Total	Horti-pasture			Total
	Marginal	Small	Semi-medium		Marginal	Small	Semi-medium	
A₁ (1501-1801)	12 (80.00)	13 (86.67)	14 (93.33)	39 (86.67)	12 (80.00)	15 (100.00)	14 (93.33)	41 (91.11)
A₂ (1801-2101)	11 (73.33)	13 (86.67)	14 (93.33)	38 (84.44)	11 (73.33)	13 (86.67)	14 (93.33)	38 (84.44)
A₃ (2101-2401)	12 (80.00)	13 (86.67)	14 (93.33)	39 (86.67)	13 (86.67)	14 (93.33)	14 (93.33)	41 (91.11)
A₄ (2401-2701)	10 (66.67)	12 (80.00)	13 (86.67)	35 (77.78)	13 (86.67)	15 (100.00)	14 (93.33)	43 (93.33)
Total	45 (75.00)	51 (85.00)	55 (91.67)		49 (81.67)	58 (95.00)	56 (93.33)	

Figures in parentheses are percentage to total

Table 2: Socio-economic status of farmers category at different altitudinal zones of Mandi district (H.P).

Family structure				
	Marginal	Small	Semi-medium	Mean
A₁ (1501-1801)	5.47	5.66	6.70	5.94
A₂ (1801-2101)	4.87	5.66	6.23	5.59
A₃ (2101-2401)	5.05	5.86	6.16	5.69
A₄ (2401-2701)	4.73	5.31	5.80	5.28
Mean	5.03	5.62	6.22	
Literacy (%)				
A₁ (1501-1801)	83.18	81.45	83.43	82.77
A₂ (1801-2101)	78.23	79.86	79.94	79.42
A₃ (2101-2401)	84.36	83.11	80.36	82.48
A₄ (2401-2701)	80.76	81.54	81.38	81.25
Mean	81.63	81.49	81.27	
Livestock status				
A₁ (1501-1801)	0.84	1.00	1.58	1.14
A₂ (1801-2101)	1.28	1.41	1.3	1.33
A₃ (2101-2401)	1.54	1.23	1.29	1.35
A₄ (2401-2701)	1.45	1.31	1.47	1.41
Mean	1.27	1.23	1.41	
Status of occupation (Agrarian people)				
A₁ (1501-1801)	2.77	3.26	2.55	2.86
A₂ (1801-2101)	3.36	3.61	3.39	3.45
A₃ (2101-2401)	3.65	3.69	3.90	3.75
A₄ (2401-2701)	3.32	3.88	3.90	3.70
Mean	3.27	3.61	3.43	
Land holding (ha)				
A₁ (1501-1801)	0.71	1.28	2.37	1.45
A₂ (1801-2101)	0.74	1.37	2.42	1.51
A₃ (2101-2401)	0.75	1.35	2.41	1.50
A₄ (2401-2701)	0.67	1.31	2.39	1.46
Mean	0.71	1.32	2.40	

Fig 1: Distribution of Apple-based Horti-agriculture and Horti-pasture Agroforestry Practices among Different categories of Farmers

Fig 2: Literacy rate among different categories of Farmers

Fig 3: Distribution of Family structure, Livestock status, Occupation and Land holdings among different Farmer categories